

Research Article

Intellectual and creative characteristics of the elderly

Aleksandr Levintov

Independent Researcher, Russia

Corresponding author

Aleksandr Levintov. PhD (Geography), Independent Researcher. Russia

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Abstract

The article shows that despite significant intellectual losses, the elderly do not lose their creativity and intellectual activity. The author provides his own example as proof of this.

Key words: Old age, creativity, intellectual activity

Introduction

The purpose of this article is to provide inspirational examples and grounds for the creativity of silver age people.

Some scientific information

Here is how psychologist O. V. Khukhlaeva characterizes a prosperous old age [4]:

- innate high intelligence, good memory
- love for others and the desire to help them
- love of life in all its manifestations
- optimism and a well-developed sense of humor
- continuing ability to create
- the ability to bring new things into one's environment
- freedom from anxiety and preoccupation

Л. Толстой lamented that the tragedy of old age is not in old age itself, but in a person's feeling of youth in old age.

The age dependence of a person's basic intellectual competencies in the interval of 32-55 years is curious [1].

Table 1: Age differences in intellectual competencies (in %)

age	attention	thinking	memory
32-33	105	104	99
34-35	100	96	96
36-37	94	96	92
38-39	97	100	92
40-41	97.5	95	92
42-43	96	86	89
44-45	95.5	93	87
46-47	93.5	89	86
48-49	86	89	83
50-51	92	91	80

52-53	95.5	91	82
54-55	93.5	89	78

Memory is most noticeably, but not catastrophically weaker, but attention (and concentration) is well preserved, which should be taken into account in the didactics of the educational process.

As for thinking, there are non-trivial processes in the range of 41-55 years old:

Table 2: Changes in the structure of thinking in adulthood

Types of thinking Age (years)	figurative	verbal	practical
41	8.1	9.0	7.3
42	7.8	7.6	5.6
43	8.3	8.4	4.8
44	9.5	9.4	5.5
45	8.5	8.5	7.1
46	8.5	8.1	5.1
47	8.7	8.7	6.4
48	8.6	8.7	6.5
49	8.2	7.5	5.0
50	7.9	8.0	4.6
51	8.6	9.1	7.8
52	7.8	7.8	5.8
53	8.9	9.3	7.3
54	8.2	9.0	7.6
55	7.4	8.2	6.3

None of the considered types of thinking (figurative, verbal, practical) tends to degrade with age, with verbal thinking retaining its priority.

Finally, the sex-age differences in behavioral characteristics are curious:

3: Gender-age differences in intellectual characteristics of adults

age	gender	creativity	breadth of cognitive needs	flexibility of behavior	subjective control
до 25	m	6.8	4.1	5.5	5.8
	f	6.5	4.2	5.0	5.4
26-40	m	6.8	3.5	5.1	5.4
	f	6.4	3.6	4.4	5.1
41-55	m	6.9	3.1	4.3	5.4
	f	6.2	3.4	4.0	4.3
свыше 55	m	6.0	3.6	3.7	4.4
	f	5.9	3.4	3.5	4.6

As the years pass, both men and women clearly lose flexibility of behavior (stubbornness grows) and self-control weakens.

A prosperous old age is accompanied by:

- high self-esteem
- fixation on positive features of one's character
- reduction of ideal and achievable self-esteem to the real level
- high level of self-esteem and responsibility

- orientation to the life of children and grandchildren (this was also noted by E. Fromm - the chances of survival in concentration camps were the longest for those who cared not about themselves, but about those left outside the concentration camp or about the work and creativity left behind).
- the retrospective nature of self-evaluation.

Here it is quite appropriate to cite Leonid Andreev's statement: "A man is born without teeth, without hair and without illusions. A man goes to the grave without teeth, without hair and without illusions".

Aphoristically, this maxim can be restated as follows:

- The formation of personality goes on throughout life, the formation of personality - in old age.

This requirement for the formation of one's own personality is the most important condition for the work of the Silver University. Society and, generalizing, mankind suffers huge losses by letting people go with the world and into oblivion without demanding and providing this design as a gift and heritage to those who remain. This is perhaps humanity's greatest intellectual and moral loss.

Poetess Nelli Brodskaya and others

Doctor of Geological and Mineralogical Sciences Nelli Grigoryevna Brodskaya lived alone in a two-room apartment in Ulansky Lane. She was practically blind, and her neighbors threw themselves together to make her a cataract operation. The operation was successful and Nellie had her sight and was overwhelmed by the beauty and colors of the world. Strongly past the age of 80, she became enraptured by the newfound beauty of the world and began composing poetry, published two collections of poetry, and won one international and one local award. She died at the age of 93, devoting the rest of her life to lyric poetry.

Here are the Stories of Grandma Nadia, Nadezhda Andreevna Minaeva, great-grandmother of Vanya and Sonya, our grandchildren, and here are my Letters to Grandson Vanya and Letters to Granddaughter Sonya. At Silver University, several students inspired by these examples wrote essays

"My Moscow" (because everyone has his own Moscow and his own tiny fragment of the city) and "My Best Journey in Life."

Philosophy of old age

Already after the launch of the Silver University we were concerned with the philosophical, worldview justification of the university's activities. In January 19, I went to a lonely Latgalian farmstead, where I wrote "The Philosophy of Old Age" in two weeks. I was helped by the local mini-Solaris, a lake with fogs walking on it. And then we conducted research and created a collective monograph "Philosophy of Old Age", both works became theoretical and methodological tools of the Moscow Silver University [2, 3].

The mission of the Silver University

The Silver University is designed to provide intellectual and creative development of people of the older generation, equip them with the necessary life competencies, professional and semi-professional skills and abilities to ensure a full and meaningful life at this stage of existence.

The social and humanitarian mission of "Silver University" is to enrich society with life experience, wisdom, accumulated worldview baggage, the value of which is determined both by this generation and younger generations. Intellectual capital is the true harvest of humanity, which must be harvested and utilized.

It is in old age that people seriously think about the meaning of their lives, and this is the main function of the elite. I always appeal to the audience of the Silver University to be concerned about their intellectual heritage, to write their intellectual testament and commandment addressed to their grandchildren and great-grandchildren, sincerely on the verge of frankness.

My old age

In general, I have lived a creatively exuberant life, although there was a 17-year failure of supposedly scientific service, drunkenness and ugliness, but at the age of 40 I came to my senses. We in the Laboratory of Regional Studies and Municipal Programs created several outstanding projects on the Danube Delta, Crimea, Mountain Altai, Shlisselburg, cities of the Vuoksa River Valley, Western Belarus. Then there were 9 years of American life. I returned from America as a pensioner. After that, we created

- VIANSА's corporate university.
- Skolkovo Moscow School of Management.
- Silver University
- Organizational Technologies Workshop
- Corporate University of Moscow City University
- concept and methodology of scientific production
- Invisible University (Ukraine)

My first book "Grub" was published when I was well over 50. Since then, more than fifty books have been published: collections of poems, literary works, scientific and philosophical studies, more than one and a half thousand scientific, popular science and journalistic articles.

In August 2021 I was fired, God will judge these people, but during this year I wrote (and it will be published soon) "Event History" (628 pages), the script of the series "Family Chronicles" (37 episodes), monthly and for many years I write 30 texts, 360 texts a year, big and small. I give lectures and lecture courses at various universities. Last year I published 20 articles in foreign scientific journals, this year - 15. This year I published two books, one of which I am the author and the other one I am the co-author. At the beginning of next year I will put two more big books into print.

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